

H2020 - Research and Innovation Action

APPLICATE

Advanced Prediction in Polar regions and beyond: Modelling, observing system design and Linkages associated with a Changing Arctic climaTE

Grant Agreement No: 727862

Deliverable No. 6.3

Provision of guidance material and tools for effective data management

Submission of Deliverable

Work Package	WP6 Data and HPC Management		
Deliverable No	6.3		
Deliverable title	Provision of guidance material and tools for effective data management		
Version	1		
Status	Final		
Dissemination level	PU - Public		
Lead Beneficiary	6 - MET Norway		
Contributors	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 – AWI	<input type="checkbox"/> 2 – BSC	<input type="checkbox"/> 3 - ECMWF
	<input type="checkbox"/> 4 – UiB	<input type="checkbox"/> 5 – UNI Research	<input type="checkbox"/> 6 – MET Norway
	<input type="checkbox"/> 7 – Met Office	<input type="checkbox"/> 8 – UCL	<input type="checkbox"/> 9 - UREAD
	<input type="checkbox"/> 10 – SU CERFACS	<input type="checkbox"/> 11 – CNRS-GAME	<input type="checkbox"/> 12 -
	<input type="checkbox"/> 13 – AP	<input type="checkbox"/> 14 – UiT	<input type="checkbox"/> 15 - IORAS
	<input type="checkbox"/> 16 - MGO		
Due Date	31 October 2017		
Delivery Date	26 February 2018		

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research & Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 727862.

Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
INTRODUCTION.....	3
1.1 Background and objectives.....	3
1.2 Organisation of this report	3
METHODOLOGY	3
RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	9

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The APPLICATE Data Portal website (<https://applicatemet.no/>) has been updated with guidance material for data providers and data centres that want to connect. This content is dynamic in the form and is accompanied by user interaction tools for communication and guidance of users. The guidance material includes links to relevant third party information as well tools and web services that are available.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background and objectives

The purpose of this task is to provide guidance material (Best practises) and tools enabling the partners to properly document and format their data in order to facilitate long term data preservation including life cycle management of data, data publication and data sharing.

1.2 Organisation of this report

First a brief description of the recommendations is provided, followed by a brief discussion. The primary information source in this context is the APPLICATE Data Portal web site which is available at <https://applicatemet.no/>.

METHODOLOGY

APPLICATE Deliverable D6.2 - Data catalogue and services provides an introduction to the data management framework set up for APPLICATE. As mentioned there, APPLICATE Data Management is distributed in nature, relying on a number of data centres contributing. These are connected using discovery metadata which are ingested in a central data catalogue. For an approach like this to work, standardisation at several levels are required.

In the Data Portal website, there is a menu marked “Support”. The content of this is shown in Figure 1. This menu provides information on both the APPLICATE Post Processing Environment as well as guidance material for data centres and data providers. It briefly introduces the concept of metadata. Frequently people think of discovery metadata as the only type of metadata. This information page presents different types of metadata and describes their purpose as well as example implementations. In order for the the APPLICATE Data Management system to work as expected, discovery metadata are required to identify the relevant datasets (i.e. the library cards) and use metadata are required to understand the data found. In this context APPLICATE (through the data portal web site) provides recommendations for standards to use.

Concerning encoding of data, APPLICATE recommends all data to be encoded in NetCDF using the Climate and Forecast Convention. Furthermore, to simplify the process of data submission to the central data storage facility it is recommended to include discovery metadata

embedded with the data using the NetCDF Attribute Convention for Dataset Discovery. If this is done, the data portal can generate Discovery metadata directly from the data.

APPLICATE furthermore recommends that data are served through OPeNDAP which allows integration of data across data repositories as it is linked to a generic data model. It also supports data streaming into applications (e.g. Matlab, R, Python) used for analysis.

Discovery metadata technologies utilised will e.g. be OAI-PMH (exchange of metadata) and ISO19115/GCMD DIF (metadata standards).

All these aspects are described in more detail through the web page. Screenshots of the information provided are presented below (Figure 2-Figure 5). This approach allows for a more dynamic user interaction where external services may be linked and made available for the user along with an issue tracker and a page for frequently asked questions.

The information on how to encode data (Figure 3) includes information and links to relevant software for data centres enabling machine interfaces to data as well as tools that the data providers can use to test the datasets they have encoded.

For more detailed information please visit <https://applicate.met.no/>.

Figure 1: The drop down menu of Support exposed.

Figure 2: Information on various types of metadata.

Figure 3: Information on how to encode data (both discovery and use metadata).

Figure 4: Information for data providers that want to submit data. A submission interface is under development, but given the volumes involved this is probably not a scalable solution for this community.

Figure 5: Information for existing data centres on how to integrate with the APPLICATE Data Portal.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The APPLICATE Data Portal website (<https://applicate.met.no/>) has been updated with guidance material for data providers and data centres that want to connect. This content is dynamic in the form and is accompanied by user interaction tools for communication and guidance of users. The guidance material includes links to relevant third party information as well tools and web services that are available. Following the dialogue with the APPLICATE community in both the Kick Off meeting as well as the 2018 General Assembly, it has proven difficult to really get in touch with the community early in process. Thus it is believed that a web based approach which is easier to modify according to user feedback is a better approach forward.